

ISic1643

I.Sicily inscription 1643

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova,Valentina Mignosa

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Catacomb of S.Giovanni

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 26631

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Felix fideli[s]
2. in pace emi mi[h]i
3. locu(m) a d[i]aconu

Apparatus

Text after Agnello 1953

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 493931

EDCS 12700071

Bibliography

Agnello, S.L. 1953. Silloge di iscrizioni paleocristiane della Sicilia. Rome. At no.80

undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-
Notizie degli scavi di antichità. *Notizie degli scavi di antichità*. At 741 no.17
Manganaro, G. 1993. Greco nei pagi e latino nelle città della Sicilia romana tra I
e VI sec. d.C.. In Calbi, A., Donati, A., Poma, G.(eds.), *l'epigrafia del villaggio*.
Faenza. pp. 543-594. At 583-584 fig.21 and 587

Licensed under a Creative
Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-18): ISic1643. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI
edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4354700>